

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

INTERNATIONAL MARKETING IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE GLOBAL FOOD AND ENERGY CRISIS CAUSED BY ARMED CONFLICTS AND THE INTRODUCTION OF ECONOMIC SANCTIONS

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Abstract

The main question we are dealing with in the work is how to adapt the traders of agricultural products, energy products from the Russian Federation and Ukraine to the crisis caused by the Russian "special military intervention" and the introduction of various packages of sanctions against the Russian Federation and how the resulting crisis affects Europe, Africa and Asia. Given that in crisis situations, very little attention is paid to marketing activities towards consumers, because the resulting changes affect decision-making and purchasing behavior in different ways. During a crisis, communication with clients is not usual because good practices are not established.

Keywords: sanctions, crisis, agricultural products, energy, inflation.

Introduction

Marketing activities in cases of major crises caused by various disturbances in the global market should be adapted to building lasting relationships with clients, communicating with more empathy, authenticity. Given that market disruptions occur frequently, marketers should not panic and stop marketing activities. Marketers can focus on increasing company value, be creative and think long-term. Therefore, marketers need to adjust their efforts, tone of communication and marketing strategies to the current situation.¹ In these situations, marketers must adapt their goals to lead generation. Traders need to prove to the market that their brand is not primarily about profit, but that their priority is their clients. Many researchers point out that marketing in times of crisis is an exercise in customer retention and brand reputation management. If the marketing mix activities are properly planned, the long-term benefits will be more significant than the temporary loss of income.

In crisis conditions, the CSR action plan for corporate social responsibility is applied. Many CSR strategies create benefits during a crisis. Most often, they increase customer loyalty and significantly improve brand reputation.

Introduction of international sanctions against the Russian Federation in response to Moscow's "Special Military Operation in Ukraine"

By definition: "international sanctions represent unilateral non-violent actions undertaken by states against another state for political reasons, which may be economic, diplomatic or military". Sanctions are in-

troduced to force another country, in this case the Russian Federation, to fulfill certain obligations or to give in to negotiations.

The introduction of a series of Western sanctions against Russia disrupts the economic and financial situation in the market, creates panic in the markets, destroys the banking system, creates a shortage of goods and a sharp rise in retail prices. Sanctions produced a global crisis, which in many countries led to accelerated inflation and a decline in living standards. As an epilogue to the sanctions, the price of energy products increased on the global market: oil, natural gas, coal, electricity.

For now, there is no real oil embargo in the countries of the European Union. If they decide to ban the import of fuel, it will lead to a large number of companies going bankrupt, a sharp increase in unemployment and inflation with unfathomable chaos in the economy.

The application of EU sanctions against the Russian Federation has some effects. However, many sanctions packages, especially in the financial sector, did not have any harmful synergistic effects, but on the contrary, they stabilized and strengthened the Russian national currency. The value of the ruble against the dollar on August 24, 2022. is 59 rubles for 1 dollar. Let's also note that the Russian ruble was worth 133.5 rubles to the dollar in March 2022. This means that the introduction of sanctions only produced a downward trend in the Russian currency for a short time. After the consolidation, the Russian currency is getting stronger. Western countries assumed that "a collapse of the Russian economy and insolvency seemed imminent."

However, the strong ruble produced higher retail prices. Since the beginning of the year, some products have risen in price by 50 to 70%. Today's ruble keeps

¹ Insightly - American computer technology company, San Francisco, California.

inflation at 20%. Many economists believe that the current exchange rate is not marketable. The ruble has been strengthened by many measures of the Central Bank, among which are restrictions on foreign exchange trade. In this way, savings in rubles and not in foreign currency increased. The discount interest rate is currently 14%. Namely, the record surplus is considered to be the main reason for the strong exchange rate. According to some estimates, by the end of the year Russia would have a surplus of about 250 billion dollars due to high energy prices. From the export of gas and oil, Russia earns billions in foreign currency that cannot be spent at all. This is why Russia has introduced gas payments for Europeans in rubles.

It should also be noted that the Central Bank predicts that the Russian gross domestic product will fall by 8 to 10% this year. Earlier expectations were for growth of 2 to 3%.

Russia directed its energy exports to new markets in Asia. This primarily refers to India, China and Iran, France, the United Emirates and Saudi Arabia. According to a report by the independent Center for Energy and Clean Air Research (CREA), Russia earned \$97 billion from fossil fuel exports in the first 100 days of the war in Ukraine. 61% of the total export of energy products was exported to Europe, for which Russia was paid 59 billion dollars.

The armed conflict in Ukraine is having ongoing effects on the world economy, which is already struggling with COVID-19 and climate change. According to the presented projections of UNCTAD² it is estimated that the world economy will have a lower GDP growth than expected. Given that Ukraine and the Russian Federation produce about 30% of the world's wheat and barley, one-fifth of the corn and more than half of the sunflower oil needs.³ Also, according to UNCTAD data, the Russian Federation is the largest exporter of natural gas and the second largest exporter of oil. Together with Belarus, Russia exports about a fifth of its needs for artificial fertilizers. Thus, the crisis in Ukraine contributed to a huge increase in the price of goods around the world. United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)⁴ report that the price of food has increased by 34% compared to last year. The price of crude oil has increased by about 60%, while the prices of gas and artificial fertilizers have tripled.⁵

The European Union's needs for natural gas in 2019 amounted to 560 billion m³, while slightly less than 200 billion m³ was delivered to gas pipelines from Russia. The import of liquefied gas was 21 billion m³. The remaining quantities needed by the European Union were delivered from Qatar 32.7 billion m³, Algeria

30 billion m³, the USA 17.7 billion m³ and Nigeria 15.7 billion m³.⁶ Therefore, the export of Russian natural gas to EU countries amounts to about 35.6% of the total European consumption.

According to Eurostat data, in 2020 the EU met 58% of its energy needs through imports, and the largest supplier of gas, oil and coal, the main raw materials in the Union's energy mix, was the Russian Federation. The import of energy from the Russian Federation in 2020 covered 24% of the EU's needs. More precisely, 35% of the energy mix is imported oil and oil derivatives, 24% natural gas, 17% renewable energy, 13% nuclear energy and 11% solid fossil fuel. According to the data of the European Statistical Service, in the EU, Russian gas had a share of 46% of imports and oil and oil derivatives of 26%.

The crisis in Ukraine disrupted global supply chains, increased transport costs, so that global inflation rose to 5.2%.⁷ According to the 2022 Financing for Sustainable Development Report, "60% of low-income least developed countries are at high risk or in debt".⁸

Export of agricultural products in crisis conditions

According to the statistics portal <https://www.statista.com/>, the global volume of wheat production in 2021/2022. year was 778.6 million metric tons. The Russian Federation and Ukraine are among the most important producers of agricultural products. 75.5 million metric tons refer to the Russian Federation and 33 million metric tons to Ukraine. In 2021, the Russian Federation and Ukraine are grouped among the world's top three exporters of wheat, corn, canola and sunflower oil. Also, the Russian Federation is the largest exporter of nitrogen fertilizers, the second producer of potash fertilizers and the third producer of phosphorus fertilizers.⁹

In the conditions of the Russian "special military operation", the question arises: how does the war affect Ukraine's export of wheat needed by Europe, Africa and Asia? Large quantities of Ukrainian grain are "captured" on the Polish-Ukrainian border. Transporting wheat by land by road or rail is complicated and time-consuming and significantly more expensive.

After the recent agreement between Russia and Ukraine, mediated by Turkey and the United Nations, regarding the export of Ukrainian wheat through the sea corridor, high insurance premiums were imposed. The export of Ukrainian grain was prevented by the blockade of the Russian navy and Ukrainian sea mines. Based on the agreement, the first ship exported 23,000

² United Nations Conference on Trade and Development UNCTAD-Conference of the United Nations on Trade and Development. The primary objective of UNCTAD is to define rules that apply to all aspects of development, including trade, aid, transport, finance and technology.

³ UNCTAD (2022), The Impact on Trade and Development of the War in Ukraine, BRIEF NO1, p. 3.

⁴ United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)

⁵ Bloomberg & MarketWatch Data, 8th of April 2022.

⁶ <https://www.grenef.com/potrebe-evrope-za-gasom/>, retrieved: 16.05.2022.

⁷ United Nations, Inter-agency Task Force on Financing for Development (2022). Financing for Sustainable Development Report 2022.

⁸ Ibid, p. xiii

⁹ Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nation THE IMPORTANCE OF UKRAINE AND THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION FOR GLOBAL AGRICULTURAL MARKETS AND THE RISKS ASSOCIATED WITH THE WAR IN UKRAINE, Information note, June 2022.

tons of wheat under the World Food Program to Ethiopia and other parts of Africa to prevent famine. According to data from Ukraine, 600,000 tons have been exported to the global market so far.

Ambitious estimates are coming from Ukraine that they will achieve revenues of over 5 billion euros, which will be generated by additional export potential.¹⁰ Since the security of the sea corridor is relative, the costs of transportation vary daily. According to the data presented by the Ukrainian company from Odessa "BPG Shipping", at the beginning of the implementation of the wheat export agreement, the insurance premiums were 4 to 5% of the market value of the ships for a period of 7 days, and today it is at the level of 1 to 1.5%, which amounts to an average of \$200,000 to \$270,000 per week. To all this combinatorics, we should add the renting of ships from Russia, which are more expensive than Romanian ones by 10,000 euros per day. The inspection of ships carried out in Istanbul additionally increases the costs of Ukrainian exporters. Therefore, the export of a ton of cargo going by sea costs Ukraine 25-35 dollars more than from Romania.

On the other hand, Russia expects a record wheat income of over 90 million tons. Since the Russians are able to give discounts on grain, they have pushed Ukrainian out of other markets such as Turkey and Egypt. The same thing happens with sunflower oil. Many Ukrainian factories are unable to process sunflower seeds, so they are forced to export unprocessed sunflower seeds, which greatly reduces their income.

Food experts estimate that another 18 million tons of grain are in Ukrainian silos. The problem for corn is especially highlighted because there will be a shortage of capacity in the silos for about 10 million tons. If there are no exports and international support for Ukraine, there will be big problems. Many researchers agree that in order for Ukraine to get out of the grain problem, the EU and the US need to bear the costs of reinsurance, so that Ukrainian exports become more competitive.

Turbulent energy prices caused by the crisis in Ukraine

The resulting events in Ukraine create energy uncertainty in terms of energy supply. According to data presented by The New York Times, in recent years energy funds have grown up to 18.4% in the first half of the year and as such were the best sector to own in 2021.

Political factors also affect the price of energy, reaching a daily high of almost \$140 per barrel on March 7, 2021. Given that the imposed sanctions prohibit the import of Russian oil into the EU, excessively high prices cause recession and economic slowdown for a long time.

The price of Russian liquefied natural gas has increased significantly today compared to the period before the start of the "special military operation" in Ukraine and the imposition of sanctions on the Russian Federation. In addition to gas, the price of electricity also increased. German benchmark power for next year rose by 2.8% to 369 euros per megawatt-hour on the

EEX exchange.¹¹ EU countries without Russian gas and high prices are facing major economic problems. In the middle of August 2022, the price of gas on the stock exchange recorded an incredible growth, \$3,600 for 1,000 cubic meters, so it represents an all-time record.¹² According to the data of the Russian news agency TASS Russian News Agency, the price of gas for delivery in April (futures contracts) increased at the Dutch hub to 3,639.1 dollars for 1,000 cubic meters or 322 euros per MWh. The price of oil on the stock exchange in mid-August 2022 is 100 dollars and electricity is 600 euros per megawatt-hour.

Conclusion

In the paper, we pointed out that all actors in the crisis understand the importance of the changes in the global market and that the implementation of marketing strategies is related to retaining clients and improving the reputation of the brand. We have shown that military conflicts and the introduction of sanctions create crises that produce unrealistic price jumps, shortages and turbulent relations on the global market. The increase in the prices of energy and agricultural products causes inflation. We have observed that in cases of crisis, marketing activities must be adapted to building lasting relationships with clients and not to temporary loss of income.

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¹¹ Source: Bloomberg.com

¹² Source: ICE Stock Exchange London.